

Analysis of minerals in bakery products - Flame Photometry

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ABSTRACT: Various brands of biscuits were studied to ascertain the percentage composition of minerals by flame photometry. The sample solutions were aspirated into the flame and were analysed for the presence of sodium, potassium and calcium in their atomic forms. The metals were introduced into the flame and the emitted light intensity was measured in the range 500nm to 800nm. The wavelength determined the presence of the element and the colour of the flame indicated the presence of the elements in the samples. The presence of calcium was indicated by a brick red colour flame measured in the range 550-650nm. Crimson colour flame measured in the range 750-850nm indicated the presence of potassium. For the analysis of sodium measurements were made in the range 550-650nm and the flame emitted yellow light.

Results of the investigation were found to be accurate and reproducible.

Key Words: Flame Photometry.

1. INTRODUCTION

Approximately 98% of calcium is found in human bones. Sodium, potassium and calcium are involved in neutral conduction and muscle contraction. HCl in stomach influences solubility and absorbability of many minerals from foods in the diet [1]. Ca, Na and K are few of the dietary macro minerals and have specific functions in the body. The deficiency of these minerals can cause body malfunctions. Correct levels of these minerals are essential for normal cell function and any changes in the levels can effect nervous system and heart and sometimes can be fatal [2]. The typical daily diet contains 130-280 mmol (8-15 g) sodium chloride. The body requirement of Ca and Na is for 1-2 mmol per day, so the excess is excreted by the kidneys in the urine. The human body requires about 50-150 mmol/day of K [3-5]. Trace minerals include Fe, I, Zn, Cu, Cr, Mn, Mo, F, Se, Si, which play biochemical roles in maintain body functions. Ultra-trace elements include V, Sn, Ni, As and B.

2. METHODOLOGY

2.1. FLAME PHOTOMETRY:

Flame photometry is based on the measurement of light emitted when a metal is introduced in to the flame. The wave length of the color indicates the presence of the element and the intensity of the color gives information about the amount of the element present.

PRINCIPLE:

The flame photometer consists of a flame of temperature around 2000°C [6]. The flow rate of the fuel gas and the oxidant gas is properly controlled and atomizer is used to obtain fine drops of sample solution which is sent in to the flame. The radiation emitted by the flame is passed through a monochromator and then to detector which measures the intensity of the spectral lines.

Sample is sprayed into the flame and is converted into droplets. Due to the thermal energy of the flame, the solvent in the droplets evaporate leaving behind residue, to give free neutral atoms or radicals. These atoms are excited by thermal energy and are unstable at the excited state, so they return to the ground state emitting photons of specific wavelength radiation. The wavelength of the radiation emitted is characteristic of elements which helps in identifying the elements qualitatively. The intensity of the radiation emitted depends upon the concentration of the elements (quantitative analysis).

2.2.Preparation of Mineral Solution of Sample:-

Different brands of biscuits were purchased from the local market at Hyderabad air dried for about 3 hours in hot air oven and powdered.

About 5gms of samples are weighed accurately in a crucible [7-8]. The crucible is heated till all the material is completely charred followed by heating in a muffle furnace for about 5-6hrs at 600°C. It is then cooled in a dessicator and weighed to ensure completion of ashing. The crucible is again heated in muffle furnace for 1/2hrs and cooled. This process is repeated till almost white or greyish white colored ash is obtained. The above obtained ash is dissolved in warm conc.HCl and HNO₃ solution. Then diluted to 100ml with double distilled water. Thus obtained mineral solution used for determination of various metals by using flame photometry.

2.3. Preparation of stock solutions:

Calcium:

2.497gms of CaCO₃ was dissolved in few ml of HCl and volume is made up to 1lt using double distilled water .This solution contains 1mg of Ca/ml.

Sodium:

2.542gms of NaCl was dissolved in few ml of HCl and volume is made up to 1lt using double distilled water .This solution contains 1mg of Na/ml.

Potassium:

1.909gms of NaCl was dissolved in few ml of HCl and volume is made up to 1lt using double distilled water .This solution contains 1mg of K/ml.

2.4. Preparation of testing standards solutions:

Calcium:

From the above prepared stock solution, testing Standard solutions were prepared by diluting to give five solutions containing 100ppm, 50ppm, 30ppm, 20ppm and 10 ppm of Ca ions and each of these solutions is introduced into the instrument and concentrations are noted.

Sodium and Potassium:

From the above prepared stock solution, testing Standard solutions were prepared by diluting to give five solutions containing 30ppm, 20ppm,10 ppm,5ppm and 2ppm of Na and K ions and each of these solutions is introduced into the instrument and concentrations are noted.

$$\text{Amount} = \text{Conc.} * \text{M.Wt}$$

3. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION:

Brick red color emitted by the flame indicates the presence of calcium, presence of sodium is indicated by the emission of yellow colored light and potassium emits crimson color light. Concentration (ppm) and amount (mg/100gm) for Ca , Na and K are shown in the tables.1,2,3 respectively.

Table-1

S.no	Sample	Conc.(ppm)	Amount of Ca (mg/100gms)
1	Sample -I	07	280
2	Sample -II	03	120
3	Sample -III	06	240
4	Sample -IV	09	360
5	Sample -V	10	400

Table-2

S.no	Sample	Conc.(ppm)	Amount of Na (mg/100gms)
1	Sample -I	05	115
2	Sample -II	09	207
3	Sample -III	08	184
4	Sample -IV	04	92
5	Sample --V	06	138

Table-3

S.no	Sample	Conc.(ppm)	Amount of K (mg/100gms)
1	Sample -I	03	117
2	Sample -II	06	234
3	Sample -III	04	156
4	Sample -IV	05	195
5	Sample -V	06	234

Calibration plots were prepared for the said samples by plotting a graph taking concentration (ppm) shown by flame photometer on Y-axis vs. volume of 100ppm solution taken to prepare 50 ppm,30ppm,20ppm,10ppm as shown in the graphs 1,2 and 3 for calcium, sodium ,potassium respectively .The concentrations of unknown solutions were determined from the calibration graphs.

4. CONCLUSION:

In the present study flame photometric studies were done for the presence of sodium, potassium and calcium in different brands of biscuits .The presence of calcium was found to be more in sample V, sample IV has more amounts of sodium and

samples II and V were found to have more amounts of potassium. The method was found to be more appropriate, less time consuming and the results were reproducible [9-10].

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6. REFERENCES

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